

PROBLEMS IN THE INTERPRETATION OF FOLK DANCES

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Annotation. This article explores issues of tradition and innovation in contemporary choreographic activities. The inevitability and necessity of the process of stylization, while maintaining the traditional basis of folk games today, is justified.

Keywords: folk dance, stylization, folk direction, means of expression.

Introduction. Dance art is a socio-cultural phenomenon that actively affects many aspects of human life in modern society. His educational role is clear and has been proven for a long time. Dance art evokes spiritual and moral qualities in a person, forms moral-aesthetic views, patriotic feelings, teaches to distinguish the original, present from the alien and familiar.

Dance may have merged with traditional crafts and other forms of art in ancient times as an element of culture. Dance, which arose within the framework of syncretic ritual movements and had certain social functions, then arose as a separate type of folk Practical Art of its own.

Folklore, one of the traditional forms of folk culture, is a genetic code, the samples of which determine the character of nations, perception of the world, social relations, spiritual values. There is a folk-amallian art, songs, dances, language of each nation, expressing the identity of the people. Traditional culture is considered to be the historical heritage, human roots that lead to this very ethnic group.

In an era of increasing globalization, integration and interaction of cultures of different peoples, it is traditional culture that serves to preserve the identity of the nation, not to lose ethno-cultural identity, to support spirituality, to strengthen the national identity. Traditional artistic culture today is becoming a real participant in the return to the people of their historical memory and pride [1]. Consequently, it is very important to take care of the culture of the people, preserve, study its samples, convey them to future generations.

Folk applied art has also accompanied man on his path to progress for thousands of years.

Art responds to the spiritual needs and aesthetic ideas of each era, and as an artistic reflection of reality in the last century and in each generation, is formed under the influence of changes in the social, economic, political and

spiritual life of society. Art is still fun, lifelike for people today.

Modern art is forced to look for the most diverse, but increasingly influential and effective forms of reflection of life in harmony with today, which meet the needs of society.

Thus, traditional (folk) culture became part of today's national culture.

Today, many choreographers turn to folk styles. This is different from the previous choreographic views of the world, which allow each creator to understand as he feels.

The well-known Georgian folk dance ensemble Sukhishvilli and Ramishvilli could not resist the attack of time.

Videos showing the new approach of Contemporary Ensemble leaders to traditional art are common, delivering to a variety of reviews: from admiration to total misunderstanding and rejection.

For thirty to forty years, the traditional folk dance has undergone such a serious change in the activities of the leaders of amateur communities that it has become very difficult to attribute it in principle to one genre. The variety of folk dance directions and combinations, Active Dynamics, mobile variability, thoughtless, superficial changes of the traditional primary source do not allow today to distinguish specific genre directions in amateur folk dances. The essence and interpretation of the concepts of "stylization", "genre", "direction", "style" are becoming ambiguous.

Incorrect, sometimes unacceptable, mixing of expressive means when creating a dance composition does not allow us to attribute these methods of work to the method of stylization.

Such compositions at competitions and festivals not only go through the qualifying rounds, but also shake the prizes!

The pace of modern life, with the strong influence of various media, has created a new personality in rapidly developing marriage and its needs. A person seeks an endless renewal of his emotions, overcoming stereotypes, expects bright, deep impressions from art, is amazed by the boldness of the idea, new forms. Today, traditional forms of culture in the form of folklore or ethnic dance are hardly found in the cultural environment. The modern man considers them archaic, outdated. As you know: each generation has its own songs, its own rhythms. Moments come when reality itself prompts the artist to look for new forms, because the old ones are not enough to reflect a new stage in the history of the people. Artistic stylization is becoming an urgent phenomenon - a natural and inevitable process of dialectical development of

art, which implies the use of artistic forms and styles already encountered in creative activity in a new meaningful context in order to achieve certain aesthetic goals [2]. Stylization enriches traditional art with new forms and means of expression while maintaining continuity between the past and the present. Due to the stylization of folk dances, music is always perceived as a refreshing, vibrant art. Archaic forms representing them disappear, new and modern ones appear. In relation to traditional folklore, its directions are novelty, “remake” (reworking), acting as a kind of distinct style.

In the second half of the 20th century, new, modern dance forms - folk directions-entered both professional art and amateur art.

One of the first reform - choreographers who harmonized traditional dance with modern dance was a talented choreographer, actress, dancer, graduate of the Tashkent choreographic educational institution Zebo Amina-Zode. In 1979, his famous dance “O sanam” was presented by the artists of the ensemble “Zebo” [3].

Despite the fact that the ensemble is 40 years old, today the dance attracts with its lyricism, softness and elegance. The feeling of mutanness, strict adherence to the chosen style was evident in the master's work.

The dances presented as an example differ from each other in terms of ideological content, images, pace, technique, styles, baletmaster technique. In general, all choreographers combine two styles in one dance-folk and modern, the latter prevail. But this does not cause a state of dissonance, dysgarmonia. Each dance is perceived as an organic whole, where mutual introduction, synthesis, synthesis of elements of different styles work to improve the composition.

In amateur groups, everything is not so clear. In the post-Soviet space, in the work of the leaders of amateur teams, a constant tendency to rule-violations remains-that is, to overcome simple attitudes, mayors and laws. In the subjective understanding of the genre of aesthetics - the absence of any principles in creativity is observed. Each choreographer seeks to establish himself in art, defending his right to creativity and modernity. Ignoring the laws of stylization, or rather ignoring or not knowing, is replaced by a claim to freedom of creation. Dance styles are endless, mixed, holistic, hybrid, synthetic choreographic forms, and a poly stylistic genre appears, “mixed” with a touch of “false ethnicity”, “false nationalism”. Modern choreographers use acrobatics, gymnastics, classical dance elements, and modern dance directions in their work, in addition to the traditional method of folk dance. As a result, it

becomes a kind of impure tasteless dance bricolage, in which elements are used according to the principle "it's strong, I like it". The mechanical, tasteless combination of elements of different styles, orientation towards brightness, attractiveness, external effect leads to the idea that behind the external dubious originality of performances, the creative style of the choreographer is hidden, not novelty, but simple unprofessionalism.

For stylized folk dances, folk choreographic folklore-compositions based on folk music, which are completely processed in the language.

Such a conclusion was reached by the analysis of dance performances by groups participating in various competitions and festivals held in large quantities in the post-Soviet space. The composition presented by the team of the dance house "Kuvirkom" (Rostov-on-Don) "used stylized folk music" "Silen polyvayet" [4]. A clear understanding of the idea of the performance is not being formed. With the help of incomprehensible plasticity, dressed in white sundresses, with no combed hair, teenage girls try to convey to the viewer the search, Hattie of adults. The composition gives rise to uncertain (purely subjective) feelings and assumptions according to its structure.

In the competition "ID City Show" (St. Petersburg) choreographer B. Shipulin presented the composition "Sokolonko", which was staged to a stylistic ethnic Belarusian song. The suit, consisting of a green sundress, a white sweater and a wreath on the head, is usually suitable for Belarusian folk music. However, the dance text does not observe Belarusian folk dance movements, but there are a lot of high batsmen. The climax of the dance is expressed as follows. Performers standing in the circle hold their hands. Every second girl turns sharply in a vertical direction with her legs and hangs in this position on the hands of neighboring performers, while her skirts fall on their heads and open under their skirts [5].

Some choreographers remain within the framework of the stylized folklore-stage dance and perform unreasonable actions, not taking into account their "nationality". Ukrainian movements add to Russian dances, Caucasian kneeling rotations (ensemble "happy childhood", Navoi sh., Uzbekistan. Balletmeister F.Musayeva).

"Musical bridge" festival-competition E.V. The dance "Russian Motifs" was performed by the exemplary stylistic and pop dance ensemble "Elegy" (Ufa, Bashkortostan) led by Koroleva. [6]. The dance is bright and cheerful. However, neither the orientation of the group to the stylization genre, nor the name of the dance referring to the nation, the participants wearing bright

short sundresses - the masculine behavior of the girls: deep sittings, dervish movements, steps in the air have no hint of Russian motifs.

Most of the director-choreographers in the amateur teams have higher education, and sometimes they have a master's degree. A question arises. What are future choreographers taught at universities?"

High-class specialists in choreographic universities are very sensitive to traditions and are afraid of losing the real, universal and national aspects that they managed to preserve in the process of stylization. Students are taught how to treat ethnic material with care, what artistic methods to use in the staging of folk dances, etc. Probably tired of creating in a narrow corridor, the graduating choreographers, intoxicated by the long-awaited independence, "I am a creator! That's how I see it, I want it! It's amazing and the audience loves it!" they plunge into the depths of anarchic freedom with desperate enthusiasm.

Censorship of art is very important today. Competitions and festivals should be conducted with the participation of team leaders with impartial artistic analysis, qualified jury with professional and reasonable criticism.

From the point of view of the identified problems, the format of the "Joziba" project, which is shown on the ZOR TV channel of the Uzbek television channel, evokes a feeling of satisfaction. After each performance of the children's dance group, a qualified jury consisting of professional teachers, choreographers and ballet masters conducts a discussion with the participation of the group leaders. give professional advice on On the national TV channel, there is an open, qualified discussion of the activities of team captains, professional advice, that censorship, that artistic council works to maintain the stylistic purity of dance, to improve the skills and quality of the leaders of amateur teams in the art of choreography in the republic.

Tradition and innovation are the dialectical opposition of the past and the present. On the one hand, classical art education is aimed at preserving the purity of the genre and honoring traditional art. This can be achieved on the condition that the new works conform to the artistic models created by the prominent choreographers of the past and present, and to the laws of the artistic genre. On the other hand, following traditions in creativity can lead to stagnation in the minds of future choreographers, and as a result, interruptions in the development of art.

Modern mass culture is now available to everyone through media technology. The "YouTube" channel provides information on how the leaders of

amateur circles guide their work. Such a director-director's culture, knowledge, and his own ideas about what is good and what is bad in art, and immune to bad taste, are useful in inoculating against rudeness and amateurism. It is also important for the team leader to understand his moral responsibility to students, their parents, the audience and art.

Conclusion. Eclecticism in art is a natural phenomenon with a specific system of aesthetic values, determined by time. Today, choreographers should not look at the process of preserving traditions in one way or another, but in terms of preserving them. Respect for traditional dance, with careful attitude, they must see and take into account the cultural and aesthetic needs of society, be able to synthesize the heritage of folklore with the most modern forms, rhythms, colors. While the heritage of our ancestors provides great opportunities in this regard, the use of it in the path of creativity requires professional skill and literacy, high aesthetic taste and proportionality.

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